

COMPARATIVE EFFICACY OF LOW DOSE ORAL DAPSONE AND
INTRALESIONAL MEGLUMINE ANTIMONIATE WITH INTRALESIONAL
MEGLUMINE ANTIMONIATE IN THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH
CUTANEOUS LEISHMANIASIS

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Abstract

Objective: To assess the effectiveness of intralesional meglumine antimoniate and low dose oral dapsone with intralesional meglumine antimoniate in treating individuals with cutaneous leishmaniasis

Study design: Randomized Control Trial

Place and duration of study: Dermatology Department, Chandka Medical College CMC, Larkana (November 2024 to April 2025).

Methodology: Sixty patients with cutaneous leishmaniasis participated in this six-month trial conducted in the dermatology department at CMC, Larkana. The lottery approach was used to randomly split the patients into two groups. Weekly intralesional meglumine antimoniate was administered to Group-A (1-2 ml of meglumine antimoniate have 405/5ml active antimony injected into every lesion depending on size) while Group-B got weekly intralesional meglumine antimoniate together with a low dose of oral dapsone (1-2 ml of meglumine antimoniate have 405/5ml with dapsone 25 mg initially for 1 week, it was then increased to 50 mg) Participants received treatment for 16 weeks or until full clinical remission whichever came first. They were assessed for effectiveness at weeks four, eight, twelve, and sixteen of the therapy. If a patient in either group had full response—that is, full re-epithelialization, settling down of erythema, induration and scaling/crusting with residual post inflammatory hypo or hyperpigmentation, as determined by a clinical examination and photographic record, the treatment was considered effective. Data was analyzed by using SPSS statistical package version 26 software. Quantitative variables were reported through mean \pm standard deviation, whereas, frequencies and percentages were calculated for categorical variables. Chi-square test was applied to compare the efficacy between the two groups. P-value \leq 0.05 was taken as significant.

Results: Sixty patients were included in this study i.e 30 in each group. The mean age in Group-A was 30.17 ± 6.30 years and in Group-B, it was 30.83 ± 5.55 years. In both groups, most of the patients were male i.e. 86.6% in

group-A and 83.3% in group-B. The two groups were not significantly different in terms of age, gender, size, site and type of lesion. Excellent response found in Combined group i.e Intralesional meglumine antimoniate with low dose oral dapsone was found to be higher (76.6%) than Intralesional Meglumine Antimoniate alone Group ($p = 0.000$), with 16 weeks' treatment.

Conclusion: Combination treatment with low dose oral dapsone and intralesional meglumine antimoniate was more effective in treating cutaneous leishmaniasis.

INTRODUCTION

The intracellular parasite that causes cutaneous leishmaniasis (CL) is spread to humans through sand fly bites. It is endemic in America, Asia, Africa, and the Mediterranean area. Globally, there are 0.7 and 1.2 million new cases of cutaneous leishmaniasis annually. The reported prevalence of CL in Pakistan ranges from 1.6 to 2.7%, with the northwest region experiencing an incidence of 4.6 cases/1000 individuals year during the previous ten years.² There are both dry and wet variants of the old world cutaneous leishmaniasis. *Leishmania tropica* is frequently associated with dry, urban or late ulcerative form.³ Clinically, the lesion typically begins as a small, erythematous papule that gradually enlarges over 6 months into a well-demarcated, indurated plaque or nodule. The surface of the lesion remains dry, crusted, and after 8-12 months, the lesion starts to regress and the ulcer heals with scar. The "wet, rural, or early" ulcerative form, frequently is caused by *L. major*. Clinically the lesion begins as a firm erythematous dome shaped nodule at site of inoculation, lesion rapidly enlarges over a period of days to weeks, forming a plaque that subsequently ulcerates. The resulting ulcer covered by crust composed of hyperkeratotic, dried exudate, live and dead parasites. with raised, indurated margins with surrounding inflammation, satellite papules, or secondary bacterial infection may be present in some cases. Unlike the dry form, wet lesions evolve more rapidly and may heal within 2 to 6 months, typically leaving a hypopigmented, atrophic, or depressed scar. The other forms of leishmaniasis are diffuse cutaneous leishmaniasis, leishmaniasis recidivans, and mucocutaneous leishmaniasis.^{4,5}

Despite the fact that CL is a vector borne parasitic infestation of tropics and sub tropics, therapy is required to stop the spread of the disease and the development of scars, particularly in exposed areas.⁶

For CL, a variety of therapeutic approaches have been employed, including as topical medications, systemic therapy, cryotherapy and thermotherapy, etc.^{7,8} According to WHO recommendations, pentavalent antimonial therapy is the gold standard for treating the condition. Nevertheless, its use is limited because of its limited availability, high cost, severe side effects like cardiotoxicity, nausea, vomiting, pain at injection site, myalgia and arthralgia.⁹

A number of therapy approaches, including local and systemic treatment. Local therapies are (cryotherapy, intralesional antimonial, thermotherapy, topical paromomycin). Systemic medications are (sodium stibogluconate, pentavalent antimonial, liposomal amphotericin B, multifosine, azoles and dapsone) and physical treatments, have been tested recently with varying degrees of success. Dapsone is one of the systemic medications it works through cytokine pathway, improve cellular immunity and change the alternative complement pathway.¹⁰

There still exists a literature gap on trials combining second line treatments with intralesional MA. In our quest for an effective early cure of the disease, we examined the combined effect of low dose oral dapsone with intralesional meglumine antimoniate, to see if the combined effect produced better therapeutic result. Our objective was to compare the efficacy intralesional meglumine antimoniate alone with low dose oral dapsone and intralesional meglumine antimoniate in patients presenting with cutaneous leishmaniasis.

Methodology:

Following clearance from the hospital's Ethical Review Committee (ERC/2024/DERM/24) and registration in the Iranian Registry of Clinical Trials (IRCT registration number: 80285), this randomized controlled trial was conducted in the Dermatology

Department of Chandka Medical College (CMC), Larkana. Following written informed consent, 60 CL patients of either gender, aged 16–60 years, with confirmed diagnosis of disease although on smear or skin biopsy for histopathology, four or less lesions, and no lesion larger than 4 cm were included using a non-probability sampling approach. Exclusions from the trial were individuals with a history of liver illness, lesions at areas that warrant systemic antimonials, sporotrichoid spread, G6PD deficient individuals, use of any systemic anti-leishmania medication during the previous three months, pregnant or nursing women, and patient having antimonial allergies. Further, patients who discontinued the treatment were also excluded. OPENEPI calculator was used to calculate the sample size of study by taking the prevalence of CL i.e. 2.7%, margin of error = 5%, then calculated sample was 60 patients which were divided into two groups (30 in each group).

Using the lottery approach, the CL patients were divided into two groups randomly. Group-A patients were treated with weekly intralesional meglumine antimoniate, whereas Group-B patients received weekly intralesional meglumine antimoniate together with low dose oral dapsone (first 25 mg/day for one week, then 50 mg/day after that). Each patient underwent complete medical examination, laboratory test with complete blood count, hepatic and renal function test, ECG, G6PD levels. Participants received treatment for 16 weeks or until the full clinical remission, whichever came first. They were

assessed for effectiveness at weeks four, eight, twelve, and sixteen of the therapy. The final response, at 16th week, was graded as excellent for 91-100% reepithelization of skin ulceration and/or flattening of the skin along with disappearance of induration, good for 75-90% reepithelization of skin ulceration and/or flattening of the skin along with reduction of induration, fair for 50-74% reepithelization of skin ulceration and/or flattening of the skin along with reduction of induration and poor response for less than 50% of re-epithelization of skin ulceration and/or flattening of the skin along with reduction of induration as determined by a clinical examination and photographic record, the treatment was considered effective. Data was analyzed by using SPSS statistical package version 26 software. Quantitative variables were reported through mean and standard deviation, whereas, frequencies and percentages were calculated for categorical variables. Chi-square was applied to compare the efficacy between the two groups. P-value ≤ 0.05 was taken as significant.

Results:

Sixty patients were included in this study (30 in each group). The mean age in Group-A was 30.17 ± 6.30 years and in Group-B, it was 30.83 ± 5.55 years. In both groups, most of the patients were male i.e. 86.6% in group-A and 83.3% in group-B. The two groups were not significantly different in terms of age, sex, size, site and type of lesion. (Table#1).

Table#1: Descriptive Data of the Patients

CHARACTERISTICS	GROUPS		P-VALUE
	Group-A (n=30)	Group-B (n=30)	
Age	30.17 ± 6.30	30.83 ± 5.55	0.666
Gender			0.717
• Male	26 (86.6%)	25 (83.3%)	
• Female	04 (13.3%)	05 (16.6%)	
Site of lesion			0.590
• Face	9 (30%)	7 (23.3%)	
• Neck	9 (30%)	14 (46.6%)	
• Upper limb	7 (23.3%)	6 (20%)	
• Lower Limb	05 (16.7%)	3 (10%)	
Size of Lesion:			0.601
• ≤ 2 cm	14 (46.6%)	11 (36.6%)	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > 2 cm 	16 (53.3%)	19 (63.3%)	
No. of Lesion: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ≤ 3 >3 	09 (30%) 21 (70%)	10 (33.3%) 20 (66.6%)	0.781
Type of lesion <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ulcerative Non-ulcerative 	13 (43.3%) 17 (56.6%)	14 (46.6%) 16 (53.3%)	0.795

Excellent response was found in combined group i.e Intralesional meglumine antimoniate with low dose oral dapsone to be higher (76.6%) than Intralesional Meglumine Antimoniate alone Group (p = 0.000), with 16 weeks' treatment, as shown in Table 2 & Figure#1.

Table#2: Comparative efficacy of low dose Oral Dapsone and Intralesional Meglumine Antimoniate with Intralesional Meglumine Antimoniate alone in the Treatment of Patients with Cutaneous Leishmaniasis

Groups	Response				P-value
	Poor	Fair	Good	Excellent	
Group-A	01 (3.3%)	15 (50%)	07 (23.3%)	07 (23.3%)	0.000
Group-B	0 (0%)	01 (3.3%)	07 (23.3%)	22 (76.6%)	

Figure#1: Pre and Post assessment of combination group (Oral Dapsone & Intralesional meglumine antimoniate)

Discussion:

Cutaneous leishmaniasis is a poverty related neglected tropical disease. Pazoki et al. conducted study in Herat Afghanistan found that the average number of cutaneous lesions was 1.54+1.45 and that men age 15 to 25 were more often.¹¹ In their research on CL in Pakistan, Bashir et al. found it was more prevalent in men.¹² This might be explained by the nature of the work. Wijerathna Tet al conducted study in Sri Lanka discovered that people who live in places suitable for sand fly resting and reproducing are more likely to become infected.¹³

The treatment of cutaneous leishmaniasis despite the fact that a wide variety of oral, parenteral, topical, surgical, and cryotherapy had been tried in the past with conflicting results in various studies. Pentavalent antimonial compounds, sodium stibogluconate and meglumine antimoniate, are still the drugs of first choice. The two compounds have almost similar efficacy and toxicity. Parenteral administration of meglumine antimoniate showed variable efficacy from 65% to 95% in various studies.²⁻¹²

Intramuscular meglumine antimoniate combination treatments are more effective than single therapy modalities, resulting in lower therapeutic doses, shorter treatment durations, reduced costs, and less side effects.¹⁷⁻¹⁹ The current study compared the effectiveness of low dose oral dapson with intralesional meglumine antimoniate and intralesional meglumine antimoniate alone in patients presenting with Cutaneous leishmaniasis and found that the combination of low dose oral dapson with intralesional meglumine antimoniate is more effective than the intralesional meglumine antimoniate alone, which is consistent with other studies.²⁰ Further, this study revealed that combination of oral Dapsone and intralesional meglumine antimoniate showed excellent response 76.6% cases with 16 weeks treatment. Al-Mutairi et al documented Dapsone (100-150 mg daily) as monotherapy showed good to excellent response in 43.8% (7/16) of CL patients.²¹

Itraconazole combined with dapson, imiquimod, or cryotherapy had a cure rate of 56.41% overall, whereas combination treatment was successful in 69.56% of patients, according to a research comparing the cure rates of these drugs alone and in combination.¹²

According to a research by Dogra et al, 80% of patients responded to therapy when oral dapson was administered at a dose of 2 mg/kg/day for 21 days, and no recurrence occurred during the next six months.²² Similarly, Ahmad N and their colleagues used dapson 2.5 m /kg/body weight/day/per mouth (maximum 200mg per day) for the treatment of CL, excellent response was observed in 54% of the cases however, side effects were observed in 5 cases this may be due to usage of high dose.⁷

For cutaneous leishmaniasis, a study comparing the effectiveness of niosomal dapson gel and intralesional meglumine antimoniate with cryotherapy and intralesional meglumine antimoniate demonstrated that the combination of these two treatments was as effective as the standard treatment, which included cryotherapy and intralesional meglumine antimoniate. No recurrence was noted in either group over the twelve months of surveillance¹⁰

Lack of leishmania species identification and absence of follow-up are study limitations. It is advised that in order to validate or refute the findings of this study, comparable multicentric studies supplemented by species identification may be carried out.

Strengths of our study are randomization, adequate sample size and similarity between demographic features in the two groups, which increase reliability and stability of our results.

Conclusion:

Combination treatment with oral dapson and intralesional meglumine antimoniate was very effective in treating cutaneous leishmaniasis with no side effects. Not much literature is available on this topic, so it is suggested that in future further studies be conducted with more sample size to validate the findings of our study. The sample size of our study was very small, so there is a need to conduct further trials on large sample sizes.

Conflicts of interest: No conflicts of interest exist.

Ethical Declaration: Approval was obtained from the ethical review committee of the hospital [ERC/2024/DERM/24]

Patients' consent: Written informed consent was provided by the patients

Authors Contribution:

JR: Design of the work, acquisition, analysis, interpretation of data and final approval

IA: Drafting the work, final approval, revising it ethically

AR: Drafting the work, revising it critically and ethically

NA: Drafting, Data collection

FK: Interpreted data and results

DP: Critical revision and final approval

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